

The origin of the cosmic ray

Yunchuan Tian¹, Zhenyuan Tian²

¹ China, tyc84110124@sina.com

²The Department of Software Engineering, McGill University, 845 Rue Sherbrooke O,
Montréal, QC H3A 0G4, Canada

Abstract

We found that solar neutrinos with energy of about 10 MeV have perihelion effect, and protons with energy above GeV of AMS-02 also have perihelion effect, so it is believed that solar energy produces cosmic rays with energy above GeV. We propose a neutrino collision model for the origin of cosmic rays. This model can reasonably explain the problem that the proton flow in cosmic rays is much greater than the electron flow.

Introduction

The origin of cosmic rays has not been clear for hundreds of years [1]. Some people think that there is a particle velocity mechanism in the solar coronal hole, but the results of the PSP solar detector [2] show that the He content in the coronal hole is higher than outside the coronal hole. We believe this refutes the idea that there is a particle velocity mechanism in coronal holes. Because if there is a particle velocity mechanism in the coronal hole, then protons are easy to accelerate, and there should be more protons in the hole, causing the He content to decrease. This is contrary to the experimental results. Experimental results show that coronal matter is a deceleration medium for particles. Tian [3] proposed that ultrahigh pressure produces high-energy particles. Tian [4] proposed that solar neutrinos produce above GeV high-energy particles. This article will further improve the theory of the origin of cosmic rays.

Theory and discussion

Figure 1. Quoted from the cosmic ray database [5]: AMS-02-p.

Neutrino collision model: The ultra-high pressure inside the sun produces high-energy electron neutrinos. The electron neutrinos turn into $\mu\tau$ neutrinos near the surface of the sun (neutrinos are first-level cosmic rays). The $\mu\tau$ neutrinos collide with ions in the solar atmosphere to produce protons, particles, electrons, and other secondary cosmic rays. Particles produced by the Sun should have a perihelion effect: i.e. the flow will be greater as one approach of perihelion. Experimental evidence can be found in the cosmic ray database [5]: AMS-02-p,

2011.12.17-2012.01.02 to 2012.06.23-07.19.

2012.12.29-2013.1.24 to 2013.06.09-07.05.

2014.12.28-2015.01.23 to 2014.06.22-07.18.

2015.12.14-2016.01.09 to 2015.06.08-07.04.

2016.12.26-2017.01.21 to 2016.06.20-07.16.

more flux at perihelion. See Figure 1.

The sun's high-energy cosmic rays are mainly above 1GV and below 20GV, and the perihelion effect is obvious. Cosmic rays below 1GV are greatly affected by solar activities, and the perihelion effect is irregular. Cosmic rays above 20GV are produced by celestial bodies outside the solar system, and the perihelion effect is very small. Based on the neutrino collision model, massive stars outside the solar system will produce high-energy cosmic rays (20 GeV-Tev). Including neutrinos, protons, particles, electrons, heavy atomic nuclei, etc.

The number of protons in the corona is basically the same as the number of electrons, so the flux of particles produced is proportional to the cross section of the particles. In the corona with a temperature of one million degrees, the cross section of protons is: $2 \times 0.84 \times 4.67 \times 10^{-4} c \Delta t = 7.85 k (\text{fm})^2$, 0.84 is the radius of the proton, $4.67 \times 10^{-4} c$ is the speed of the proton at a temperature of 1 million degrees, Δt is unit time, $k = 10^{-4} c \Delta t$, c is speed of light.

The weak-action radius of electrons is inversely proportional to energy. The weak-action radius of electrons is approximately $(1.68 - 0.32) \times 10^{-4} \text{ fm}$, $1.68 \times 10^{-4} \text{ fm}$, which corresponds to the weak-action radius of electrons when $\sqrt{s} = 91.187 \text{ GeV} (m_z)$, $0.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ fm}$. Corresponding to the weak-action radius of electrons when $\sqrt{s} = 209 \text{ GeV}$, the speed of electrons at a temperature of 1 million degrees is $2 \times 10^{-2} c$, Δt is unit time, and the action cross section of electrons is:

$$2 \times (1.68 - 0.32) \times 2 \times 10^{-2} c \Delta t = (0.067 - 0.0128) k (\text{fm})^2, k = 10^{-4} c \Delta t.$$

Therefore, the ratio of proton flux to electron flux in cosmic rays is around 117-613. The actual measurement is shown in Figure 2.

Why is the flux of electrons in cosmic rays much smaller than the flux of protons? Because the universe is electrically neutral, this is a question that any cosmic ray theory must answer.

Figure 2. Quoted from the cosmic ray database [5]: AMS-02-p/e.

The energy spectrum of the proton produced by the neutrino collision is similar to that of the neutrino, and both can be described by equation (3).

SK[6] measured the flux of $\nu_{\mu\tau}$ neutrinos around 10 Mev in the sun to be: $3.45 \times 10^{10} / \text{m}^2 \text{s}$.

From equation (1), use $\alpha = 2.6$ to calculate the flux of $\nu_{\mu\tau}$ neutrinos in Gev generated by the sun: $2.18 \times 10^5 / \text{m}^2 \text{s}$. From Figure 6 and Figure 11 of K2K[7], it can be calculated that the neutrino detection rate of SK detector $f_l = 1.3 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2 / \text{kt}$, then we can calculate how many solar Gev neutrinos there are in the 33kt atmospheric neutrino experiment of SK[8]: $n = 2.18 \times 10^5 \times 1.3 \times 10^{-13} \times 33 \times 535 \times 24 \times 3600 = 43$.

The measured value of Sk[8] atmospheric neutrinos is 50-70, and some of the neutrinos originate from the sun. sk[9] experimental data show that from 1996 to 2000, the solar neutrino flux on July 5 (aphelion) was significantly smaller than the neutrino flux on January 5 (perihelion), showing that the sun was about 10 Mev Neutrinos also have a

perihelion effect. But directly measuring GeV solar neutrinos will require more and larger detectors.

In [3] I is the flux of cosmic rays, $I = k\Delta v$, Δv is the reaction zone, and its radius is R .

$$\text{Only when } \Delta V \text{ is a sphere can : } I = k/E^\alpha, \alpha = 3 \quad (1)$$

For stellar-mass black holes, the interaction region is nearly spherical. However, absorption by the surrounding gas leads to a cosmic-ray spectral index of $\alpha=3.1$, with cosmic-ray energies ranging from 1 PeV to 1000 PeV (see Fig. 1 in [10]).

For supermassive black holes, the interaction region approximates a spherical surface. The resulting cosmic-ray flux has a spectral index of $\alpha=2$, with cosmic-ray energies exceeding 1000 PeV.

$$I = k/E^\alpha, \quad (2)$$

Due to absorption by surrounding gas, the cosmic-ray flux has a spectral index of $\alpha=2.2-2.3$. Cosmic-ray particles are produced in a spherical shell around a stable star. When the thickness of the shell is 10%–20% of the stellar radius, the resulting particle energy spectrum is:

$$I = k/E^\alpha, \alpha = 2.6 \quad (3)$$

The energy of cosmic rays from various stars ranges from 1 GeV to 1000 GeV. The energy of cosmic rays from the Sun is below 30 GeV, as shown in Fig. 2 of [11].

The energy of cosmic rays from neutron stars ranges from 1 TeV to less than 1 PeV, and their energy spectrum is slightly softer than that of ordinary stars, with $\alpha=2.6-2.7$.

The pressure near the surface of a neutron star cannot turn matter into neutrons, so no neutrino flow is produced. When matter falls onto the surface of a neutron star, high-energy gamma rays ($<1\text{PeV}$) are produced due to bremsstrahlung radiation. High-energy gamma rays can produce secondary cosmic rays. High-energy gamma rays can also produce antimatter (negative protons and positrons) when they collide with atomic nuclei. Supernova explosions(1987a) only produce low energy ($<100\text{Mev}$) antineutrinos.

The ultra-high pressure near the black hole event horizon can turn matter into neutrons. When matter falls near the black hole's event horizon, the matter first turns into neutrons to produce a neutrino flow (first-order cosmic rays), and then the neutrons fly towards the black hole's event horizon due to Bremsstrahlung produces high-energy gamma rays (which

are also first-level cosmic rays), so black holes are high-energy neutrino sources and high-energy gamma ray sources (>PeV). At this point, the first-level cosmic rays only have neutrinos and gamma rays. The second-level cosmic rays produced by the first-level cosmic rays include protons, particles, electrons, heavy atomic nuclei, antimatter ions, secondary gamma rays, and secondary neutrino et al. Secondary cosmic rays can produce third-level cosmic rays in the earth's atmosphere.

The symmetry of the gamma-ray bubbles at the center of the Milky Way suggests that black holes are among the most powerful sources of gamma rays. These gamma rays are produced when matter falls into a black hole. The gamma-ray energy emitted by this supermassive black hole can exceed 1000PeV. The gamma rays observed on Earth are secondary emissions, produced when ultra-high-energy gamma rays interact with gas, with energies in the range of 1–100 GeV.

Conclusion

1. The perihelion effect of the proton flux of AMS-02 proves that solar energy produces cosmic rays with energy above GeV.

2. The flux of GeV-level neutrinos produced by the sun should be around

$10^5 / \text{m}^2 \text{s}$. Some of the GeV-level neutrinos currently measured in the atmosphere originate from the sun. Neutrinos around 10 MeV from the sun also have a perihelion effect.

3. Because the universe is electrically neutral, why is the electron flux in cosmic rays much smaller than the proton flux? Only the neutrino collision model can reasonably explain it.

4. Only when the cosmic ray originates from the ultra-high-pressure region does its flux exhibit a power-law distribution.

Author contributions

Y.T. proposes a theory ; interpreted the data; and substantially revised the manuscript. Z.T. interpreted the data and drafted the manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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